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Effectiveness of foliar application of Zinc, Iron and Boron on growth and yield of Sponge gourd (*Luffa cylindrica* L.)

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Abstract

The present research was carried out to evaluate the effects of micronutrients such as iron, zinc and boron on growth and yield of sponge gourd (*Luffa cylindrica* L) at Vegetable Research Area, Institute of Horticultural Sciences, the University of Agriculture Faisalabad during the year of 2018. Research was accomplished by Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with 3 replications, each replication contained 30 plants and each treatment contains 3 plants. Data was recorded for date of first harvest, flower colour, fruit size (cm), fruit yield per plant (kg), number of fruit per plant, fruit set percentage (%), fruit length (cm), total soluble solids (⁰borix), electrical conductance (s), titrable acid (%) and pH. The results regarding the growth of sponge gourd were found significant. The treatment T4 (0.75g foliar spray of Boron) found best for fruit diameter (14.45mm), fruit length (26.3cm) as compared to control treatment (without foliar spray). Zinc and Iron also increase the fruit length and fruit diameter. Fruit yield per plant (1.75 kg per plant), average fruit weight (170.09gm), number of fruits per plant (9.66), fruit set percentage% (75.26 %) and male and female flower ratio of sponge gourd were found significant for the foliar application of Zinc, Iron and Boron. All the above observations that were observed from that foliar spray of micronutrients increase the growth and yield of sponge.

Key Words: Sponge gourd, Zinc, Iron and Boron, growth and yield.

Introduction

Cucurbits, is a familiar name that is given to a number of crop vegetables that belong to the cucurbitaceae family. Cucurbits have sprawling nature and broadly grow all over the dry and semi-dry regions and comprises of the biggest amount of vegetables that produce in summer and rainy season. Sponge gourd possesses its own value among all the cucurbitaceous vegetables. Sponge gourd is an essential cucurbit crop broadly cultivated in Pakistan. It produces more male flowers than the female flower. Different names given to sponge gourd like a loofah, bath sponge or cloth gourd vegetable sponge and Gujarati grower called it Galaka (Bharadiya *et al.*, 2018).

When sponge gourd was grown in moderate areas, it needs hot summer and high frost-free sprouting period. Optimum PH required by *L. cylindrical* is about 6-6.8 (Oboh *et al.*, 2009). *Luffa cylindrica* is summer season vegetable, the monoecious, male flower is with unbranched inflorescence and one female flower is also present. *Luffa cylinderica* fruits are green, and large cylindrical in shape that is crawl on other materials (Partap *et al.*, 2012). The stem of sponge gourd is green in colour with crawling nature and angular in appearance (Lee and Yoo, 2006). Growth habit of luffa sponge gourd plants resembles cucumbers (*Cucumis sativus* L.).

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Considerable production increases could be obtained by preparation cucumbers to a vertical trellis rather than raising them on the ground.

According to a nutritionist, sponge gourd comprises an essential component of human nourishment. The daily requirement of an adult's total food is 284g per head that is around 20%. (Solangi *et al.*, 2009). It is used in AIDS treatment which can be linked to the presence of proteins such as luffaculin with ribosome-inhibiting properties on the replication of HIV infected lymphocyte and phagocyte cells (Otimenyin *et al.*, 2008).

Micronutrients are well-known to act as a stimulant in stimulating organic reactions that are taking place in plants and also to develop the plant condition (Patil *et al.*, 2013). Micronutrients application can increase the resistance of plants against environmental pressure (Cakmak, 2008). Foliar propagation is an efficient form for the application of certain micronutrients, as they are used in a small amount. Micronutrients do not precisely connect with soil, prevent depletion by fixation. Foliar applications of micronutrients in raised crops will guarantee the more excellent crop nourishment at anthesis and stage of seed filling that sequentially boost the yield of seed. Foliar utilization of micronutrients to crop plants is gaining popularity in increasing crop yield and quality of improving the shelf life of the produce (Karthick *et al.*, 2017).

Micronutrients such as iron, zinc, boron etc., have been reported to play a vital part in modifying the growth and development of many horticultural crops. They develop an overall state of plants that are well-known to react as a stimulant in stimulating organic responses taking place in the plant.

Zn is the chief alignment of ribosomes and is important for their advancement. Zn scarcity causes the decay of amino acids that are stored in plant tissues and the production of protein. Zinc also has a vital role in biomass production (Cakmak, I. 2008). Moreover, zinc might be mandatory for the production of chlorophyll, pollen role and fertilization (Kay and Higgs, 2002).

Boron is the essential nutrient for maximum yield, development, growth and condition of crops (Shireen *et al.*, 2018). Iron is the most important for the perpetuation of chloroplast shape and its role and also involved in the synthesis of chlorophyll in plants. Iron is the 3rd most needed nutrient for plant metabolism and growth because in aerobic environments, iron is less soluble due to its oxidized ferric form (Zuo and Zhang, 2011; Samaranayke *et al.*, 2012). The boric acid is utilized as the source of B, which shows the vital character in the development of the plant, constancy of membrane, cell wall structure, phenol and carbohydrate digestion than the transport of sugar (Brown *et al.*, 2002).

Keeping in view the present study was carried out to see the Effects of Fe, Zn and B on growth and yield of Sponge gourd and to compare the effectiveness of different micronutrients for the morphological characters and growth of *Luffa cylindrica*.

Materials and Methods:

The present research was accomplished at Vegetable Research Area, Institute of Horticultural Sciences, the University of Agriculture Faisalabad during the year..... Seeds of sponge gourd were collected from Sohail Sons Dijkot Road Faisalabad and sown in both sides of beds during summer. A field experiment was carried out to study the effects of Zinc, Iron and Boron on growth and yield parameters of sponge gourd (*Luffa cylindrica* L.). There were 10 treatments of micronutrients applied with different concentrations by foliar spray and one is control treatment. The first foliar spray was applied after 30 days after sowing (DAS), the second spray after 45 days and the third spray was applied after 60 days of sowing. application of micronutrients. T0 (Control), T1 (1gm H₃BO₃/1L water), T2 (2gm H₃BO₃/1L water), T3 (3gm H₃BO₃/1L water), T4 (1gm ZnSo₄/1Lwater), T5 (2gm ZnSo₄/1Lwater), T6 (3gm ZnSo₄/1Lwater), T7 (1gm FeSo₄/1Lwater), T8 (2gm FeSo₄/1Lwater) and T9

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(3gm FeSo₄/1Lwater). Recommended doses of irrigations and fertilizers were given to the crop when required. Moreover, according to the required standard, plant protection measures were employed to keep insects and diseases controlled. When the fruit was getting ready to harvest, they were harvested, with the calibration of 2-3 days and some quality parameters would be analyzed and recorded. Research was accomplished subsequent Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with 3 replications, each replication contained 30 plants and each treatment has 3 plants. Data were analyzed by ANOVA techniques and means were compared by using the LSD test at 5% probability level (Steel *et al.* 1997).

Results and discussion

Foliar spray of Zn, Fe and B improved the growth and yield in plants and reduced the insufficiency of micronutrients. Though, as the concentration of these micronutrients increased, plants show the adverse effects and growth of plants retarded. The high concentration of micronutrients reached the toxic level. Foliar spray of Zn, Fe and B improved the yield of fruit, fruit number, fruit weight, size and length of fruit, fruit diameter. The observation concerning the growth of *Luffa cylindrica* L. was substantial. The treatment T₃ (0.75g foliar spray of Boron) was found best for the diameter of fruit 14.45mm, length of fruit 26.3cm. these findings are higher than that of control treatment in which no application of micronutrients applied. Fruit yield and individual fruit weight were obtained best by the 0.75g application of Boron 1.75 kg per plant and 170.09g. Foliar spary of Zinc sulphate and iron gave low yield than boron but higher than control. It might be due to the concentration of dose either high or low as it is discussed that a high dose of micronutrients leads to effect the plant growth and yield. The number of fruits per plant was expressively increased by the foliar spray of Zn, Fe and B. Maximum fruit no. was obtained from T₃(0.75g spray of Boron). Fruit set percentage highly influenced by micronutrient application. The highest percentage of fruit set was recorded from the 0.75 g foliar spray of Zn (68.00) Fe (73.66) and B (75.33), whereas the minimum percentage of fruit set was observed from the control treatment (40.900). Male and female flower ratio (7.02) from control treatment followed by T₁ (0.25g foliar spray of Boron) 6.63. Least proportion to male to female flower was obtained from 0.75 g of boron (4.29) and 0.75 g of zinc (3.39). The male and female flower ratio is precisely associated with the entire no. of antheral and carpellate blossom, which is ultimately linked to yield of *Luffa cylindrica*. All micronutrients used exogenic considerably minimize the expression of sex as compared to control.

Results showed that the maximum Titratable acidity was observed from 0.75g of boron (4.3 g/ L) while the minimum level of TA was observed 2 g/ L. Increased Zn and Fe concentration increased the TA of fruit. It is well known that Fe plays a key role in carbohydrate metabolism and fruit quality. Maximum enhancement in the TSS contents of fruits was obtained from the T₁ (0.25g foliar spray of boron) 7.6 Borix⁰ followed by the T₆ and T₉ (0.50g and 0.75g foliar spray of zinc and iron respectively) which is higher than that control treatment 6.1 Borix⁰. Statistical analysis shows that the pH of fruit gradually deduction and becomes acidic as the concentration of micronutrients is increased as compared to control treatment in which no application zinc, iron and boron have pH 6.5. Maximum deduction in pH by application of T₃ and T₉ (0.75g foliar application of boron and Iron) 5.1 followed by the T₆ and T₇ (0.25g and 0.75g application of Iron and Zinc) 5.2 and 5.3 respectively. While the minimum decrease in pH has been shown by the application of T₅ (0.50g application of Zinc) 6.2.

From this result, it can be concluded that the foliar application of micronutrients effects the growth and yield of sponge gourd. Foliar spray of 0.75 g of boron remained best for all traits followed by the zinc and iron. All these micronutrients showed the best results than the control treatment. Our findings are in agreement with Kaya and Higgs. 2002, Kazemi, M. 2013. Karthick *et al.* 2018, Kadu *et al.* 2018, Ibrahim *et al.* 2007, Fozia *et al.* 2018, Bharati *et al.* 2016, Patil *et al.* 2008. The highest TSS content might be due to the higher concentration of micronutrients in leaves and fruits, which might have boosted the accumulation of assimilates resulting in

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better quality parameters. Singh *et al.* (2002) mentioned that micronutrients had an effect on T.S.S and the quality of fruit.

Table 1. Effect of zinc, iron and boron on yield contributing traits of sponge gourd

Treatments	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit diameter (mm)	Fruit weight (g)	Yield/plant (kg)	Yield/ha (kg)	Fruit set percentage (%)	Male & female flower ratio (%)	Fruits/plant
Control	17.000 e	8.920 j	144.98 f	1.2800 i	459.06 i	40.900g	7.0200 a	7.333 d
H ₃ BO ₃ 0.25g/L	21.000 cd	10.910 ef	160.67 c	1.6100cde	577.42cd	53.000 ef	6.6300 ab	10.00 cd
H ₃ BO ₃ 0.50g/L	25.000 ab	12.840 bc	166.00 bc	1.6500 cd	591.76cd	63.327 cd	4.4800 ef	12.00 bc
H ₃ BO ₃ 0.75g/L	26.333 a	14.450 a	170.09 a	1.7567 a	630.01a	75.333 a	4.2900 def	15.000 a
ZnSO ₄ 0.25g/L	23.000 bc	9.430 hi	149.67 e	1.4800 h	530.06h	51.667 ef	5.0367 de	11.000 c
ZnSO ₄ 0.50g/L	24.000 ab	11.08 cde	155.96 cd	1.5500 fg	555.89fg	58.267 def	3.9000 efg	12.66 bc
ZnSO ₄ 0.75g/L	25.333 ab	9.920 h	157.86 cd	1.6100cde	577.28de	68.000 bc	3.5000 h	14.667 ab
FeSO ₄ 0.25g/L	19.000 de	10.150 fg	148.62 e	1.5100 g	541.55 g	57.667 de	5.5333 bcd	9.667 cd
FeSO ₄ 0.50g/L	20.00 cde	11.580 cd	161.24 bc	1.5800 ef	566.74 ef	63.660 cd	5.1000 cde	10.667 cd
FeSO ₄ 0.75g/L	22.00 bcd	13.450 ab	169.33 ab	1.6900 bc	606.10b	73.667 ab	4.7100 ef	13.333 abc

Table 2. Effect of Zn, Fe and B on biochemical parameters of sponge gourd.

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Treatments	Titrateable acidity (g/L)	TSS content (Borix ⁰)	Fruit pH
control	2.9100 e	6.1000 f	6.5000 a
H ₃ BO ₃ 0.25g/L	3.7333 bc	7.6333 a	6.0000 bc
H ₃ BO ₃ 0.50g/L	3.8000 b	7.4333 bc	5.5333 de
H ₃ BO ₃ 0.75g/L	3.6000 c	6.9333 e	5.1000 f
ZnSo ₄ 0.25g/L	4.3000 a	7.3000 cd	6.2000 ab
ZnSo ₄ 0.50g/L	4.2000 ab	7.5000 ab	6.1000 b
ZnSo ₄ 0.75g/L	3.3333 d	7.2000 d	5.2000 ef
FeSo ₄ 0.25g/L	3.0000 de	7.0000 e	5.3000 ef
FeSo ₄ 0.50g/L	3.0000 de	7.4333 bc	5.7000 cd
FeSo ₄ 0.75g/L	3.2667 d	7.5667 ab	5.1000 g

Conclusion

From all the above research, it is concluded that foliar spray of micronutrients increases the growth and yield of sponge gourd. The results treatments are comprising that the B remained best from all treatments followed by Fe and Zn. All the applied micronutrients considerably increased the growth and yield than the control treatment.

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